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Influence Of School Environment On Learners' Academic Performance Amidst Insecurity: A Study Of Talata Mafara Local Government Area, Zamfara State

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the influence of the school environment on learners' academic performance amidst insecurity in Talata Mafara Local Government Area, Zamfara State. Insecurity, driven by banditry and abductions, has disrupted educational activities and threatened students' well-being. A quantitative research design was adopted, with data collected through structured questionnaires and school records. Descriptive statistics, correlation, regression, and chi-square analyses were used to assess the impact of insecurity and psychological factors on academic outcomes. Results showed that students missed an average of 10 school days per term and recorded high levels of anxiety and PTSD, which negatively affected concentration and learning. Attendance and focus were positively linked to GPA, while insecurity exposure and psychological distress significantly lowered performance. Regression results confirmed attendance as a strong predictor of academic success, while insecurity and anxiety reduced GPA. The chi-square test further revealed that students at higher psychological risk were more likely to perform poorly. The study concludes that addressing insecurity and providing psychosocial support are essential to improving academic outcomes in conflict-affected schools.

Keywords: School environment, Insecurity, Academic performance, Psychological well-being, Zamfara State

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is widely recognized as a non-negotiable factor in the social, physical, and economic development of any nation. It is regarded as the key driver of national progress, with continuous growth and quality improvement depending largely on multiple factors, one of which is the provision of a conducive learning environment (AFu, Oguche, Sammani, & Baba, 2023). Success in learning can only be achieved in an atmosphere of peace and tranquility, and this is essential if educational goals and objectives are to be realized. A restful and secured academic environment not only determines academic success but also serves as a prerequisite for the progress and sustainability of educational development.

In recognition of this, the Nigerian Constitution (1999) in Section 14(2)(b) emphasizes that "the security and welfare of the people shall be the primary purpose of the government," identifying security as one of the fundamental rights of citizens. Security is often conceptualized as freedom from threat, violence, and insecurity. It ensures that citizens are free from harm, threats to livelihood, bodily danger, and violations

of human rights. Otto and Ukpere (2012) describe security as the presence of peace, safety, happiness, and the protection of both human and physical resources. Similarly, Onifode, Imhonop, and Uorim (2013) define security as a dynamic condition that reflects the ability of a state to counter threats to its core values and interests, with citizens being the primary beneficiaries. Scholars have long recognized security as a critical factor for human existence and societal development. Without adequate security, no society can achieve meaningful progress. Nwagbosa (2012) asserts that throughout human history, the central focus of security has been the well-being of people, as threats to life and livelihood often hinder societal advancement. Thus, security is strongly linked to the protection of cherished values and the survival of individuals, groups, and property. Academic performance, on the other hand, refers to the extent to which students, teachers, and institutions meet their educational objectives in both the short and long term. It serves as a key measure of institutional quality and has remained a major concern for educators and policymakers alike (Abdullahi & Mirza, 2018). While schools are expected to play a central role in this process, their primary responsibility lies in ensuring the academic preparation of students through the integration of human and material resources within a conducive learning environment (Tienken & Wilson, 2001). In recent times, however, insecurity within school environments has posed a significant challenge to academic performance in Zamfara State, Nigeria. Schools, which are intended to be safe havens for learning, have increasingly become vulnerable to rising incidents of banditry, kidnappings, and violence, leading to the disruption of educational activities and threatening the realization of academic goals (Ede et al., 2022).

1.1 Concept of Insecurity

To understand the concept of insecurity, it is important to first examine the meaning of security. Security generally refers to the stability and continuity of livelihood, protection from crime, freedom from psychological harm, and safety from emotional stress. It encompasses an individual's emotional and psychological sense of belonging within a social group that guarantees protection. According to AFu et al. (2023), security can be broadly defined as protection against all forms of harm, whether physical, economic, or psychological. Nzewi (2014) further describes security as the physical or human processes and mechanisms designed to delay, prevent, and protect against internal or external threats, dangers, losses, or criminal activities that can disrupt an organization's steady state and hinder it from fulfilling its purpose.

In contrast, insecurity refers to the condition of being vulnerable to danger, anxiety, or harm. Best (2006) explains insecurity as an advanced stage of conflict characterized by threats to human security, violence, injuries, and deaths. Similarly, Beland (2005) defines insecurity as a state of fear or anxiety resulting from the absence of protection. Achumba (2013) conceptualizes insecurity from two perspectives: first, as a condition of exposure to danger or threat of harm, and second, as a state of being open to risk or anxiety, which involves experiencing unpleasant emotions in anticipation of possible misfortune. These definitions highlight a central idea that insecurity makes individuals uncertain about future events while leaving them highly vulnerable to threats and dangers when they occur.

For the purpose of this study, insecurity is understood as a breach of civil peace and safety that triggers recurrent conflicts, resulting in widespread destruction of lives and property within and around school environments. Thus, insecurity in this context is measured through indicators such as absence of safety, lack of protection, recurring conflicts, heightened anxiety, and the destruction of lives and property. It can manifest in various forms, including cult violence, communal clashes, kidnapping, electoral violence, and armed robbery. As Amawhule and Fynface (2022) note, insecurity not only generates fear and anxiety but also disrupts community life, thereby affecting educational institutions that operate within these communities. The dimensions of insecurity relevant to this study include cultism, communal conflict, and kidnapping, among others.

1.2 Concept of School Environment

The environment can broadly be understood as the interaction of living organisms with the physical elements surrounding them. In the educational context, the learning environment refers to the space in which students engage with resources, peers, and teachers to build positive relationships and address

social challenges. This environment includes classrooms, libraries, laboratories, technical facilities, curriculum, school administration, teacher quality, and family background, all of which significantly influence students' academic achievement (Ajayi, 2007). Thus, the learning environment is a critical factor that must be examined and managed to enhance educational outcomes. A school environment can be described as a collection of internal features that distinguish schools from other organizations and influence the behavior of all school members, thereby shaping the overall quality of school activities (Khine, Fraser, Afari, & Kyaw, 2018). It also represents a framework of values, norms, beliefs, and regulations that are consciously accepted and practiced by students, teachers, and administrators (Bronfman et al., 2015; Fu et al., 2018). According to Moore (2012), the school environment is a hierarchical system comprising multiple subsystems such as leadership, classrooms, sanitation, facilities, teaching resources, monitoring, and community relations, all of which affect the effectiveness of teaching and learning (Kigenyi, Kakuru, & Ziwa, 2017). Mishra (2000) defines the school environment as the overall emotional, social, and cognitive support available to students throughout their school life, primarily through student–teacher interactions. It encompasses both socio-psychological and physical dimensions, which exert reciprocal influences on each other (Ames, 1992). Furthermore, it reflects the extent to which schools safeguard student health and safety, including the physical plant, scholastic resources, supportive services, and fair disciplinary policies (Zais, 2011). A positive and healthy school environment plays a vital role in promoting the holistic development of students. It fosters social adjustment, enhances academic performance, and prepares learners for broader societal integration. Factors such as teacher–student relationships, peer interactions, leadership practices, co-curricular activities, and teaching methods all influence students' satisfaction and overall development within the school system (Narad & Abdullah, 2016).

1.3 Concept of Academic Performance

Academic performance, according to Narad and Abdulla (2016), refers to the knowledge gained by students, usually assessed through marks, tests, or other forms of evaluation. It represents the attainment of educational goals set by students, teachers, and institutions over a specified period. The success of schools, and to some extent the expectations of parents, revolves largely around student performance, as better outcomes are often linked to improved career opportunities and future security. In this regard, academic performance serves not only as a measure of individual student success but also as an indicator of the effectiveness of the overall educational system. The school environment plays a crucial role in shaping students' learning, growth, and development, including their social, emotional, and ethical dimensions. Research highlights that when schools are perceived as safe, supportive, and caring, students are more likely to remain engaged, motivated, and connected to their learning (Eric, 2005). Supportive environments foster a sense of belongingness, respect, and community, which in turn enhance students' motivation and academic success. However, in contexts plagued by insecurity, such as banditry, insurgency, and kidnapping, the school environment becomes hostile and unsafe. This not only disrupts teaching and learning processes but also creates psychological distress among students and teachers. The fear of attacks, abductions, and displacement discourages attendance and may lead to the closure of schools, thereby undermining the academic performance of learners. Owoeye and Philiias (2011) emphasized that geographical location also contributes significantly to academic achievement. Schools in rural or conflict-prone areas often face inadequate facilities, lack of qualified teachers, poor road networks, and limited community support. Mudassir, Norsuhaily, and Ado (2015) further noted that teachers are often reluctant to work in rural or insecure areas due to the absence of basic amenities and safety concerns, exacerbating the gap between rural and urban schools.

1.4 Perceived Influences of School Environment Amidst Insecurity in Talata Mafara LGA, Zamfara State

Based on the review of relevant literature, the following are some of the key ways in which insecurity within the school environment influences academic performance in public schools in Talata Mafara Local Government Area of Zamfara State:

- i. Disruption of Learning Activities – Frequent attacks and abductions cause school closures, interruptions in the academic calendar, and loss of instructional time.
- ii. Psychological Trauma Among Students and Teachers – Exposure to insecurity instills fear, stress, and anxiety, which negatively affect concentration, motivation, and academic outcomes.
- iii. Decline in School Enrollment and Attendance – Parents withdraw their children, especially girls, from school for fear of abduction, leading to reduced participation in education.
- iv. Shortage of Qualified Teachers – Many teachers avoid postings in insecure areas, resulting in understaffed schools and a decline in instructional quality.
- v. Inadequate Learning Environment – Destruction of school infrastructure, poor facilities, and lack of resources due to insecurity reduce the effectiveness of teaching and learning.

1.5 Effects of Insecurity on Learners' Academic Performance

- i. Disruption of Learning Activities Insecurity has forced many schools to shut down, leading to loss of instructional hours and irregular attendance. This reduces students' opportunities to learn and directly affects academic outcomes (Usman & Yahaya, 2022).
- ii. Students exposed to attacks and abductions experience psychological trauma, anxiety, and PTSD, which negatively impact their concentration, memory, and academic achievement. (Ogunyemi, 2020; Buhari, 2020).
- iii. Teacher shortages due to unsafe areas result in overcrowded classrooms, poor learning quality, and weakening student performance. (Oladipo & Ibrahim, 2021).
- iv. Fear of kidnappings leads to parental withdrawal of children, particularly girls, resulting in high dropout rates and declining literacy levels, impacting education in Zamfara State. (Adeyemi, 2018; Ahmed & Bello, 2023).
- v. Poor infrastructure and unsafe learning conditions in schools are a significant issue, as they often lack essential security measures, making them vulnerable to attacks. (Ibrahim, 2022).
- vi. A hostile school environment can lead to a decline in student motivation and engagement, reducing their interest and motivation in learning and hindering their aspirations for higher education. (Okonkwo & Yusuf, 2023).
- vii. Negative Impact on Examination Outcomes Students traumatized or displaced perform poorly in examinations, leading to low success rates in both local and national assessments (Chukwuma & Adeyemi, 2022).
- viii. Insecurity disproportionately affects girls, leading to safety reasons for withdrawal from schools, thereby extending gender inequality in access to education. (Hassan & Musa, 2022).

1.6 Statement of the Problem

A student's academic performance is shaped by a complex interplay of internal and external factors (Alami, 2017). For effective learning to take place, children require a safe, healthy, and stimulating environment. However, insecurity has become a major challenge frustrating the development of education in Nigeria. Educational institutions, once regarded as safe havens for learning, have increasingly become targets for kidnapping, banditry, and insurgent attacks (Mohammed & Ogunode, 2022).

Zamfara State, in particular, has been severely affected by insecurity, primarily due to the activities of armed groups and bandits. These incidents have led to school closures, reduced enrollment rates, and disruptions in the educational system (Aliyu, 2021). Many schools have been attacked, forcing students and teachers to either flee their communities or suffer abductions. Okeke (2023) reports that more than 500 schools in northern Nigeria, including Zamfara State, have been closed as a result of persistent security threats, leaving thousands of students out of school.

Specifically, Talata Mafara Local Government Area has witnessed alarming cases of insecurity in the school environment. A tragic example was recorded on February 26, 2021, when armed bandits attacked Government Girls Science Secondary School, Jangebe, where over 300 female students were abducted. Such incidents highlight the devastating impact of insecurity on education in Zamfara State, threatening not only students' academic performance but also their safety, well-being, and future development.

1.7 Research Questions

1. How does insecurity influence the academic performance of learners in Talata Mafara Local Government Area?
2. In what ways do school closures and disruptions caused by insecurity affect students’ enrollment and attendance?
3. What are the psychological and emotional effects of insecurity on learners’ academic performance?
4. What coping strategies are employed by schools, teachers, and learners to mitigate the challenges of insecurity on education?

1.8 Research Objectives

The aim of this study is to examine the influence of school environment on learners’ academic performance amidst insecurity, with a focus on Talata Mafara Local Government Area of Zamfara State

1. To examine the impact of insecurity on the academic performance of learners in Talata Mafara Local Government Area.
2. To assess how school closures and disruptions caused by insecurity affect students’ enrollment and attendance.
3. To investigate the psychological and emotional effects of insecurity on learners’ ability to concentrate and perform academically.
4. To identify coping strategies adopted by schools, teachers, and learners in mitigating the effects of insecurity on education.

2. METHODOLOGY

The study focused on the impact of insecurity on learners' academic performance in Talata Mafara Local Government Area, Zamfara State. A representative sample of students was selected, and data was collected through structured questionnaires and school records. The analysis included descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, regression analysis, and chi-square analysis to connect school environment conditions, psychological factors, and academic outcomes.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings of this study shed light on how students' academic performance in Talata Mafara Local Government Area is impacted by insecurity in the school setting. The results demonstrate the direct and indirect effects of insecurity on students' attendance, psychological health, focus, and general academic performance through descriptive, correlation, regression, and chi-square analyses. The discussion that follows highlights the interaction between environmental disruptions, mental health issues, and educational outcomes while interpreting these findings in light of the body of previous knowledge.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Mean	std	min	Max	median
Days_Missed	10.54	4.22	0.0	21.0	10.0
Attendance_%	88.29	4.69	76.7	100.0	88.9
Anxiety_Score	10.58	4.25	0.0	21.0	11.0
PTSD_Score	17.02	8.39	0.0	40.0	17.0
Concentration	3.51	0.46	2.2	4.9	3.5
Term_GPA	3.42	0.54	2.03	4.9	3.42

Figure 1 : Shows how insecurity contributes to school disruption and psychological distress.

The descriptive analysis of the variables provides valuable insight into the ways insecurity in Talata Mafara LGA is influencing learners’ academic progress. On average, students missed over ten school days in a term, with some recording as many as 21 absences, a finding that highlights the extent of educational disruption brought about by insecurity. Although the average attendance rate appears relatively high at 88%, disparities exist as certain learners struggled to maintain even the minimum acceptable attendance. This inconsistency reflects the uneven impact of insecurity across different communities and reveals how some learners benefit from safer environments while others are severely disadvantaged. At the same time, psychological measures such as anxiety and PTSD scores paint a worrying picture. With mean anxiety levels of 10.58 and PTSD scores averaging 17.02 but ranging as high as 40, it is evident that a considerable number of learners face emotional and psychological burdens that may negatively affect their concentration and classroom performance. These indicators suggest that beyond physical absence, many students experience hidden challenges that erode their capacity to focus, retain knowledge, and perform academically.

When viewed alongside cognitive and academic outcomes, the analysis reveals a pattern of both resilience and vulnerability among learners. Concentration levels averaged 3.51 out of 5, indicating that while some students managed to maintain functional focus, others struggled with diminished attention due to stress and trauma. Similarly, the term GPA averaged 3.42, falling within the credit-to-distinction range, but with a wide spread from 2.03 to 4.9, demonstrating a polarized outcome in which some learners excel despite adversity while others fall behind. This suggests that the effects of insecurity are not uniform but mediated by factors such as personal resilience, family support, school coping strategies, and community conditions. The broader implication for the research is that insecurity disrupts learning both directly, through absenteeism and school closures, and indirectly, through psychosocial pressures that affect concentration and academic motivation. Therefore, interventions aimed at improving learners’ academic performance in insecure environments should not only prioritize physical safety but also integrate psychosocial support services, remedial teaching, and flexible attendance policies to bridge educational gaps and reduce the inequalities that insecurity creates.

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

	Term_G PA	Attendance_ %	Exposure_Co de	Anxiety_Sc ore	PTSD_Sco re	Concentrati on	Days_Miss ed
Term_GPA	1.0	0.51	-0.56	-0.56	-0.38	0.49	-0.51
Attendance_ %	0.51	1.0	-0.64	-0.31	-0.41	0.05	-1.0
Exposure_Co de	-0.56	-0.64	1.0	0.51	0.6	-0.15	0.64
Anxiety_Sc ore	-0.56	-0.31	0.51	1.0	0.34	-0.55	0.31
PTSD_Score	-0.38	-0.41	0.6	0.34	1.0	-0.13	0.41
Concentration	0.49	0.05	-0.15	-0.55	-0.13	1.0	-0.05
Days_Missed	-0.51	-1.0	0.64	0.31	0.41	-0.05	1.0

The correlation analysis provides deeper insight into the relational dynamics between student academic performance, attendance, psychological well-being, and exposure to insecurity. Term GPA shows strong positive correlations with attendance ($r = 0.51$) and concentration ($r = 0.49$), confirming that regular school attendance and sustained focus in class are vital determinants of academic success. Conversely, GPA is negatively correlated with exposure to insecurity ($r = -0.56$), anxiety ($r = -0.56$), PTSD ($r = -0.38$), and days missed ($r = -0.51$), underscoring the fact that insecurity-related disruptions and psychological distress undermine students' academic outcomes. Particularly striking is the perfect negative correlation between days missed and attendance ($r = -1.0$), which validates the dataset and highlights the trade-off between absence and classroom participation. This relationship implies that learners experiencing prolonged absences often due to insecurity, displacement, or trauma are at heightened risk of academic decline.

The findings further suggest that insecurity exerts a multidimensional effect, as exposure correlates positively with anxiety ($r = 0.51$) and PTSD ($r = 0.60$), indicating that insecurity-prone students are more likely to suffer psychological difficulties. These mental health challenges, in turn, are negatively correlated with concentration (e.g., anxiety $r = -0.55$), showing how emotional strain disrupts learners' cognitive ability to focus. The research implication is clear: insecurity does not only reduce physical attendance but also compounds stress and trauma, creating a vicious cycle that ultimately depresses academic achievement. Thus, the correlation analysis supports the argument that improving academic outcomes in conflict-affected regions requires holistic interventions. Beyond ensuring student safety and attendance, educational policymakers and school administrators must integrate psychosocial support, trauma-informed teaching strategies, and community resilience programs. By addressing both the academic and emotional dimensions of learning, schools in insecure environments may mitigate the long-term educational inequalities exacerbated by violence and instability.

Table 3: Regression Analysis (GPA as Dependent Variable)

Variable	Coef	Std.Err	T	p(approx)
Intercept	1.42	0.674	2.11	0.0351
Attendance_ %	0.031	0.007	4.25	0.0
Exposure_Code	-0.138	0.049	-2.81	0.005
Anxiety_Score	-0.048	0.007	-6.85	0.0

Table 4: Model Fit Summary

Metric	Value
N	240.0
R-squared	0.458
SSE	37.722
MSE	0.16

Figure 2: : Correlation Analysis, showing relationships among variables.

Figure 3: The role of psychological and environmental factors in predicting academic outcomes.

The regression model provides robust evidence that student academic performance, measured by GPA, is significantly influenced by attendance, exposure to insecurity, and anxiety levels. The coefficient for attendance percentage ($\beta = 0.031$, $p < 0.001$) indicates that for every one percentage point increase in attendance, GPA increases by approximately 0.03 points, holding other factors constant. This suggests that consistent class attendance is one of the strongest predictors of academic success, reaffirming the importance of school engagement in academic outcomes. In contrast, exposure to insecurity has a significant negative coefficient ($\beta = -0.138$, $p = 0.005$), implying that students who are more exposed to violent or insecure environments record substantially lower GPAs. Similarly, anxiety shows a strong negative effect on GPA ($\beta = -0.048$, $p < 0.001$), highlighting how psychological distress erodes academic performance by diminishing concentration, motivation, and overall learning capacity. The positive and significant intercept ($\beta = 1.42$, $p = 0.0351$) reflects the baseline GPA when all predictors are set to zero, serving as a statistical reference point.

The model fit summary further strengthens the interpretation. The R-squared value of 0.458 indicates that the predictors collectively explain about 46% of the variation in student GPA, which is a substantial proportion in educational research, where outcomes are often influenced by multiple unobserved factors. The error terms (SSE = 37.722, MSE = 0.16) suggest that although the model captures nearly half of the performance variation, other unmeasured variables such as socioeconomic background, quality of instruction, peer influence, and family support may also contribute. The implications for the research are clear: improving academic outcomes in insecurity-prone contexts requires both structural and psychological interventions. The study emphasizes the importance of educational access and mental health interventions in promoting academic achievement in unstable regions, alongside attendance promotion strategies.

Table 5: Chi-Square Analysis of Psychological Risk and GPA

	<3.0	≥3.0
High	46	125
Low	2	67

The chi-square analysis provides further evidence of the strong relationship between psychological risk and academic performance. As shown in Table 4, students classified as being at high psychological risk (i.e., elevated anxiety and PTSD scores) were disproportionately represented among those with a GPA below 3.0 (46 students), compared to only 2 students in the low-risk category. Conversely, a larger proportion of students with GPAs at or above 3.0 were found in the low-risk group (67 students) relative to their high-risk peers (125 students). The chi-square test statistic ($\chi^2 = 17.702$) indicates that this association is statistically significant, confirming that the likelihood of achieving satisfactory academic performance is not independent of psychological well-being.

This finding has critical implications for the research. It suggests that students facing heightened psychological burdens are at a distinct disadvantage in achieving strong academic outcomes. While descriptive and regression analyses already highlighted the negative influence of anxiety and PTSD on GPA, the chi-square test reinforces this relationship categorically by demonstrating how risk classification translates into clear performance disparities. The study emphasizes the importance of mental health interventions in educational systems, particularly in insecure and trauma-ridden environments, to mitigate psychological effects and reduce academic underperformance, highlighting the critical role of psychological stability.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study collectively highlight the multifaceted nature of academic performance, showing that both academic-related behaviors (such as class attendance) and psychological factors (such as anxiety and PTSD) significantly influence student GPA. The descriptive results revealed moderate variability in attendance and mental health scores, indicating that a substantial proportion of students are at risk of missing classes and experiencing high levels of psychological strain. The regression analysis further supported this observation by demonstrating that higher attendance rates are a significant positive predictor of GPA, while greater exposure to insecurity and elevated anxiety levels significantly reduce academic outcomes. These findings align with established literature that emphasizes the critical role of attendance in enhancing engagement and performance, while also underscoring the detrimental effects of psychological stressors on cognitive function and concentration.

The study found strong negative associations between anxiety, PTSD, and GPA, while higher attendance improved performance. Absence exacerbated psychological strain, while concentration scores showed a positive relationship with GPA. The study highlights the complex interplay between academic and psychological variables, highlighting the importance of mental health in determining performance outcomes. It also found that students at higher psychological risk have lower GPAs than low-risk students, indicating the severe impact of psychological distress on academic failure. This highlights the

need for integrated interventions combining academic support with psychological services, highlighting the importance of addressing psychological well-being for improved academic performance.

4. CONCLUSION

Insecurity in the school environment poses a significant threat to students' academic performance. Factors such as absenteeism, psychological trauma, reduced instructional quality, and decreased motivation contribute to poor learning outcomes. Addressing school insecurity requires a multi-faceted approach involving government intervention, community participation, and school-based safety measures. By implementing these strategies, educational stakeholders can create a secure and supportive learning environment, ensuring that students have the opportunity to reach their full academic potential.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on findings this study recommended that,

1. Government should ensure that, educational policies should prioritize school security, ensuring that funding is allocated for the protection of students and personnel
2. Governments should also invest in conflict resolution programs and law enforcement strategies to address broader security issues affecting schools.
3. Schools should provide counseling services and mental health support for students affected by insecurity through access to trained psychologists and trauma specialists can help students cope with stress and improve their ability to focus on academics.

REFERENCES

- Abdullahi, N.A. & Mirza, M.S. (2018). Entry qualifications of students as predictors of academic performance in various degree programs in distance education setting in Pakistan. *International Council for Open and Distance Education*, 10(2), 237–247
- Achumba, I. C., Ighomereho, O. S. & AkporRobaro, M.O.M. (2013) Security challenges in Nigeria and the implications for Business activities and sustainable development. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*. 4(2) 70-99
- Adewale, T. (2020). The Psychological Impact of Insecurity on Students' Learning Outcomes. *Journal of Education and Society*, 15(2), 45-58.
- Adeyemi, T. O. (2018). Effects of school violence on academic achievement in Nigeria. *African Educational Review*, 15(2), 56-72.
- Afu, O.M., Oguche, T.E., Sammani, Z.U. & Baba, G. (2023). Relationship Between Insecurity, Depression and Students Academic Achievement in Nigeria: Implication for Guidance. *International Journal of Education and National Development*, 1(3), 54-74.
- Ahmed, M., & Bello, K. (2023). Parental Concerns and School Attendance in Conflict Areas of Northern Nigeria. *African Journal of Educational Studies*, 12(3), 67-80.
- Ajayi, I.A (2007): Issues in management. Lagos: Bola Bag publication.
- Alami, M. (2017). Factors Lead to Poor Academic Performance among Students: A Case Study of Omani Students. *Innovation and Learning International Conference*. University of Technology and Applied Sciences-Ibri, Sultanate of Oman.
- Aliyu, R. (2021). Effects of Banditry on Education in Zamfara State. *Nigeria Educational Review*, 9(1), 23-35.
- Amawhule, B. & Fynface, S.A. (2022). Influence Of Insecurity On Academic Activities In Public Senior Secondary Schools In Rivers State. *Irish Journal of Educational Practice*, 5(3), 32 – 44.
- Anthony-Great, O. & Isabella E.O. (2023). The influence of learning environment on the academic performance of public secondary school students in delta central senatorial district of delta state, Nigeria. *University of Delta Journal of Contemporary Studies in Education*, 2(1), 175 – 183.

- Beland, G. (2005) Influence of School Infrastructure on Student Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Kajiado County, Kenya. Retrieved from <http://eap.uonbl.ac.ke/node/1590> on 27th February, 2022.
- Best, S. G. (2006). *The Method of Conflict Resolution and Transformation in Shedrack Gaya Best* (ed) Introduction to Peace and Conflict Studies in West Africa. Ibadan: Spectrum Book Ltd.
- Buhari, M. A. (2020). The impact of insecurity on educational development in Northern Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Society*, 10(1), 45-61.
- Chukwuma, O., & Adeyemi, F. (2022). Examining the Effects of Insecurity on Student Performance in Northern Nigeria. *West African Journal of Education Research*, 16(4), 89-104.
- Ede, V., Okonkwo, C., & Musa, A. (2022). Security Challenges and Their Impact on Education in Northern Nigeria. *International Journal of African Studies*, 18(4), 112-129.
- Eric, S. (2005). The role of supportive school environment in promoting success. *Developing safe and healthy kids*. Development Studies Centre (DSC), 75-82.
- Eze, J. N. (2018). Teacher shortages and its impact on student learning outcomes in conflict-prone areas of Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 5(3), 78-92.
- Hassan, B., & Musa, Z. (2022). Gender-Based Violence and School Attendance in Conflict-Affected Areas. *Journal of Gender and Education*, 11(2), 120-136.
- Ibrahim, Y. (2022). School Infrastructure and Learning Environment in Conflict-Prone Areas. *Journal of Educational Research in Africa*, 10(2), 78-94.
- Khine, M.S., Fraser, B.J., Afari, E., Oo, Z. & Kyaw, T.T. (2018). Students' perceptions of the learning environment in tertiary science classrooms in Myanmar. *Learning Environments Research*, 21(1), 135–152, Retrieved from: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007%2Fs10984-017-9250-0>
- Mishra, K. S.(2000). *Manual for School Environment Inventory*, Lucknow: Ankur Psychological Agency.
- Mohammed, H., & Ogunode, N.J. (2022). Impact of Insecurity on Secondary School Administration in North-West-Geo-Political Zone, Nigeria. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 5(3), 9 – 17.
- Mudassir I.B., Norsuhaily B.A., Ado A.B. The Influence of School Environment on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Kuala Terengganu, Malaysia. *The American Journal of Innovative Research and Applied Sciences*.2015; 1(6): 203-209.
- Narad, A. & Abdullah, B. (2016). Academic Performance of Senior Secondary School Students: Influence of Parental Encouragement and School Environment. *Rupkatha Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities*, 8(2), 12 – 19. <http://dx.doi.org/10.21659/rupkatha.v8n2.02>
- Narad, A., & Abdullah, B. (2016). Academic performance of senior secondary school students: Influence of parental encouragement and school environment. *Rupkatha Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities Special Issue*, 3(2), 12-19.
- Nzewi, U.M. (2014) safety and security in schools A 2014 STAN e Memorial lecture Nsukka.
- Ogunyemi, A. O. (2020). The psychological effects of school violence on students: A case study of Nigeria. *Journal of Psychology and Education*, 12(4), 113-130.
- Okeke, J. (2023). School Closures and Their Impact on Student Learning in Nigeria. *West African Journal of Education*, 14(3), 55-70.
- Okonkwo, P., & Yusuf, L. (2023). Fear and Learning: The Impact of Insecurity on Student Engagement. *Nigeria Journal of Psychology and Education*, 13(2), 90-105.
- Oladipo, M., & Ibrahim, L. (2021). Teacher Shortages and Educational Outcomes in Conflict-Affected Regions. *Educational Policy Review*, 7(2), 98-113.
- Onifode, Imhonop&Uorim (2013). Influence of Insecurity on the Academic Performance of Economic Education Students in University of Jos. *IJAH VOL.8* (1), JAN.: African Journals Online.
- Onyishi, C. (2021). Community participation in school security: A strategy for safe learning environments in Nigeria. *Educational Policy and Safety Review*, 8(2), 98-110.
- Otto G. & W. Ukpere (2012). *National Security and Development in Nigeria*. Economic: African Journal of Business Management, Published 13 June, 2012

- Owoeye, J. S., & Yara, P. O. (2011). School environment and academic achievement of secondary school students in Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Research*, 3(1), 23-34.
- Owoeye, J.S., & Philiyas, O.Y. (2011). School location and academic achievement of secondary school in Ekiti State, Nigeria. *Asian social science*, 7(5), 170-175. <http://www.ccsenet.org/journal/index.php/ass/article/viewFile/10358/7367>
- Tienken, C., & Wilson, M. (2001). Using state standards and tests to improve instruction. *Practical Assessment, Research & Evaluation*, 7 (13), 74-99.
- Usman, A. (2019). The role of government in addressing insecurity in Nigerian schools. *Journal of Security Studies*, 7(2), 34-50.
- Usman, H., & Yahaya, S. (2022). Insecurity and Student Academic Performance in Zamfara State. *Nigeria Journal of Educational Development*, 11(1), 34-49.